

Effect of *Cowpea Mottle Virus* on Cowpea (*Vigna Unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) Yield Losses in Burkina Faso

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Abstract

Cowpea production is constrained by several viral diseases all over the world. In Burkina Faso, eight cowpea-infecting viruses were identified using metagenomics-based approaches, including cowpea mottle virus (CPMoV). While this virus, as yet restricted to the Sudan zone, could emerge at the country scale, we aimed in this study to determine the impact of CPMoV on the cowpea yield and to identify resistant cowpea cultivars. Nine cultivars provided by the INERA-CREAF (Institut de l'Environnement et de Recherches Agricoles) breeding program were screened by mechanical inoculation in the field during two years of the trial using split-plot design. Disease incidence, symptom severity, pods and grain yield losses were assessed. Disease incidence was extremely variable and ranged from 4.17 to 100 %. In addition, three groups of cowpea resistance against CPMoV were defined based on symptom severity, including resistant cultivars (Tiligre and Yiis-yande), susceptible cultivars (Gorom local and Moussa local) and fairly susceptible cultivars constituted by the rest of the cowpea cultivars. Aside from the resistant cultivars, the virus reduced pods and grain yields considerably. Gorom local and Moussa local were the most affected with a reduction of 42.04-76.92 % in pods number and 47.31-79.67 % in grain weight. We also report that CPMoV was not seed-transmitted by the nine cultivars. This is the first report of cowpea yield losses caused by CPMoV in Burkina Faso and the first identification of cowpea resistant cultivars against this virus. The identified resistant genotypes should be popularized and used in breeding programs to develop cowpea resistant varieties in Burkina Faso

Keywords: Cowpea mottle virus, cowpea, yield losses, resistant, Burkina Faso

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) is originated from West Africa (Vaillancourt and Weeden, 1992) where it still one of the most important subsistence crops. In this area, over two-third of the 5.6 million tons of the world's cowpea grain are produced in 2015 (Faostat, 2016). Burkina Faso remains the third world producer country with an average of 563,392 tons of cowpea grains produced annually between 2010 and 2014 (Faostat, 2016). With a content of 25-30% high-quality plant protein, 53% carbohydrates, amino-acid (lysine and tryptophan) and vitamins (Hall et al., 2003; Nielson et al., 1993), cowpea contributes to reducing protein deficiencies in smallholders diets (Modu et al., 2010). Furthermore, cowpea leaves constitute a source of quality fodder for livestock and provide cash income (Aboki and Yuguda, 2013; Langyintuo and Lowenberg, 2006).

However, world cowpea average yield remains low, 337-417 kg/ha, (Adegbite and Amusa, 2008) although it can reach 1500-3000 kg/ha under improved technologies (Agyeman et al., 2014; Aliyu et al., 2019; Dzemo et al., 2010). Cowpea yield losses are associated with abiotic and biotic constraints where viral diseases are one of the most damageable (Adegbite and Amusa, 2008; Taiwo and Shoyinka, 1988).

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Over one hundred and forty viruses can naturally or artificially infect cowpea worldwide, among which seventeen have been reported from Africa (Hampton and Thottappilly, 2003; Hema et al., 2014; Palanga et al., 2016). In Burkina Faso, to date, eight cowpea infecting viruses have been characterized including *Cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus* (CABMV), *Bean common mosaic virus-blackeye cowpea strain* (BCMV-BICMV), *Cowpea mottle virus* (CPMoV), *Southern cowpea mosaic virus* (SCPMV), *Cowpea polerovirus 1* (CPPV1), *Cowpea polerovirus 2* (CPPV2), *Cowpea tombusvirid 1* and *Cowpea tombusvirid 2* (Konate and Neya, 1996; Palanga et al., 2016; Palanga et al., 2017). Some of these eight viruses are known to cause high percentages of yield loss in West Africa, i.e. CABMV with 18-87 % (Bashir et al., 2002a; Neya et al., 2015), SCPMV with 27-57 % (Taiwo and Akinjogunla, 2006) and CPMoV with 65-75 % (Shoyinka et al., 1978; Thouvenel et al., 1990). Moreover, when these viruses occurred in mix infections, a total (100 %) yield loss was recorded (Nsa and Kareem, 2015).

The use of resistant cultivars is generally the preferred method to control viral diseases because it is durable and environmentally friendly (Boukar et al., 2016; Taiwo and Shoyinka, 1988). In Burkina Faso, genetic resistance sources have been identified and used for CABMV only (Barro et al., 2016b; Neya et al., 2015). The search for resistance to other viruses is required to improve cowpea virus control in the country.

While CPMoV represents a threat for cowpea production in Burkina Faso (Kareem and Taiwo, 2007; Nsa and Kareem, 2015; Taiwo et al., 2007), no studies on resistance of cowpea cultivars against this virus were achieved in the country.

In this study, we evaluated nine cowpea cultivars - available from a breeding program in Burkina Faso - for their resistance against a CPMoV isolate from Burkina Faso. Virus incidence, symptoms severity and yield losses were assessed and CPMoV seed-transmission was tested. Our study reveals that the nine cowpea cultivars can be classified into three disease susceptibility groups: resistant-, fairly susceptible- and susceptible-cultivars.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cowpea cultivars used

For this study, nine cultivars (table 1) were evaluated. They were obtained from “Institut de l'Environnement et de Recherches Agricoles (INERA)” cowpea breeding program in Burkina Faso. V1 to V6 and V9 cultivars resulted from crossbreeding, when V7 and V8 are local cultivars.

Table 1: Characteristics of cowpea cultivars evaluated in this study

N°	Cultivars	Origin	Virus susceptibility	References
V1	Yiis-yandé	INERA/BF	-	-
V2	Tiligré	INERA/BF	-	-
V3	Nafi	INERA/BF	Tolerant to CABMV	(Barro et al., 2016a)
V4	Gourgou	INERA/BF	Tolerant to CABMV	(Barro et al., 2016a)
V5	Komcallé	INERA/BF	-	-
V6	Niizwé	INERA/BF	-	-
V7	Moussa local	INERA/BF	Susceptible to CABMV	(Neya et al., 2015)
V8	Gorom local	INERA/BF	Susceptible to CABMV and BCMV-BICM	(Barro et al., 2016a; Neya et al., 2015)
V9	KVX 61-1	INERA/BF	Susceptible to CABMV	(Barro et al., 2016a)

INERA/BF: Institut de l'environnement et de recherches agricoles, Burkina Faso

Source and propagation of cowpea mottle virus

The cowpea mottle virus isolates BE273 isolated in 2016 in Burkina Faso on cowpea plant (Palanga et al., 2016) was used in this study. It was initially propagated by mechanical inoculation to the cowpea cultivar “Gorom local” in insect-proof greenhouses located at INERA-Kamboinsé (12°27.231 N; 001°32.371 W). After three weeks, cowpea plants presenting mottling symptoms were tested positive for CPMoV by RT-PCR as described in Palanga et al. (2016) to confirm the presence of the virus.

Experimental design

Resistance to CPMoV was screened in field conditions at INERA-Kamboinsé in two independent experiments, one from September to November (2015) and one from July to October (2016). The experimental design was a split-plot in three replicates. Two levels of treatment were applied to the plots: plots inoculated with CPMoV (IP) and non-inoculated control plots (NIP). The nine cowpea cultivars were randomly assigned to the sub-plots. After ploughing and fertilization (100 kg ha⁻¹ of NPK (14 23 14)), seeds were sown in 0.8 m spaced rows. Each row contained five 0.4 m spaced holes, and two seeds were introduced per hole.

Plant inoculation method

Plants were mechanically inoculated 12 days after sowing. Leaves of CPMoV-infected Gorom local plants grown in insect-proof greenhouses, were ground in phosphate buffer (0.05 M) at ratio 1/5 (w/v) in the presence of sterile sand. The extract was mixed with Carborundum (600 mesh) and rubbed onto the full surfaces of leaves of the nine cultivars. Plants in control plots were not inoculated.

Monitoring and data collection

Every two weeks after sowing, plants (inoculated and control) were treated with a mixture of contact (Decis: deltaméthrine, 12EC) and systemic (Titan: acetamipride, 25EC) insecticides at 4 ml/1.5 L and 2ml /1L concentrations, respectively. Otherwise, Titan is persistent for two weeks.

Assessment of symptoms severity

Both inoculated and control plants were screened every two days for CPMoV symptoms development with a disease severity scale ranging from 1 to 6 (adapted from (Gumedzoe et al., 1990)). Score 1 corresponds to non-symptomatic plants ; 2, to plants exhibiting 25 % of leaves with mild mosaic or mottle symptoms; 3, to plants exhibiting 50 % of leaves with moderate mosaic or mottle symptoms; 4, to plants exhibiting 75 % of leaves with severe mosaic or mottle symptoms ; 5, to plants exhibiting 100 % of leaves with severe mosaic or mottle symptoms and 6, to plants exhibiting 100 % of leaves with severe mosaic or mottle symptoms, distortion and stunting. At 28 days after inoculation (DAI), cultivars with severity means (SM) ranging from 1 to 2 ($1 \leq SM < 2$) were considered to be resistant; cultivars ranging from 2 to 4 were considered to be tolerant; cultivars ranging from 4 to 5 were considered to be fairly susceptible and cultivars ranging from 5 to 6 were considered to be susceptible.

Incidence (I %) of the disease and day after inoculation at which symptoms appeared (DSA) were also determined. $I (\%) = n/N$, where n is a number of plants exhibiting symptoms and N, the number of plants inoculated.

Effects of CPMoV on yields traits

To determine the effect of CPMoV on the cowpea yields, pod number per plant and seed number per five pods were scored. In addition, total seed weight per plant was measured.

Seed transmission

To assess the seed transmission of cowpea mottle virus, 180 seeds collected from symptomatic plants of each of the nine inoculated cultivars were sown in insect-proof greenhouses in containers containing sterilised soil. Seedlings (70 for cultivar Yiis-yandé, 80 for cultivar Tiligré, 88 for cultivar Nafi, 92 for cultivar Gourgou, 86 for cultivar Komcallé, 100 for cultivar Niizwé, 104 for cultivar Moussa local, 108 for cultivar Gorom local and 90 for cultivar K VX 61-1) were observed for the presence of viral symptoms during two weeks for a total of eight hundred and eighteen (818) plants. Rates of seed-transmission were determined as the number of the symptomatic plant over the germinated plant for each of the nine cowpea cultivars. To confirm or invalidate seed transmission, asymptomatic leaves were tested in back inoculation to susceptible cultivar Gorom local, as described previously.

Statistical analyses

All data collected were analysed using xlstat v. 19.02 software. Normality tests revealed that the distributions of incidence (I %), severity mean (SM) and days after inoculation at which symptoms appeared (DSA) were not normal. The Mann-Whitney test was used to compare different treatment and the Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare cultivars within each treatment. Means separation was done according to the Bonferroni test. The cultivars were then grouped based on the severity mean using the agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC). The AHC was constructed based on dissimilarity, euclidian and Ward aggregation method (1963). While the distribution of yield data was normal, analyses of variance (ANOVA) were used to compare disease and healthy plants. Means separation was done according to Tukey (HSD) test. The bilateral statistical test Z was applied to compare inoculated and non-inoculated plants. To determine a correlation between DSA, SM, incidence and yield parameters, a Person statistical test was adopted. All statistical tests were accepted at a 5 % level of probability.

RESULTS

Symptomatology

Vein chlorosis and mottling developed in inoculated plants of the nine cultivars during the first 15 DAI. At 28 DAI, while leaf distortion, leaf reduction and plant stunting (Figure 1) were observed for Moussa local and Gorom local cultivars, symptoms remained mild for cultivars Tiligré and Yiis-yande.

Figure 1: Different cowpea mottle virus-associated symptoms on cultivar Gorom local. A, vein chlorosis and mottling at 15 DAI; B, leaf distortion at 28 DAI; C, leaf reduction (encircled) at 28 DAI and D, healthy plant.

Day after inoculation at which symptom appeared (DSA), disease incidence (I %), and severity mean (SM)

- *Comparison of inoculated vs. non-inoculated cowpea plants*

All differences were very highly significant between inoculated and non-inoculated plants (Table 2). Symptoms appeared very earlier (5.37 to 6.57 DSA) on inoculated plants where the disease incidence and

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severity were high respectively (78.96 to 80.83 %) and (4.05 to 4.33). By contrast, in non-inoculated plots, virus incidence was very low and symptoms were observed so late at three weeks after inoculation date (Table 2).

Symptoms observed in non-inoculated plots might be due to probably extern contamination. However its effect might be neglected when considering the high difference between IP and NIP plants (Table 2).

Table 2: Day after inoculation at which symptoms appeared (DSA); disease incidence (I %) and severity mean (SM) in the inoculated and non-inoculated plants (Mann-Whitney statistical test).

Treatment	2015			2016		
	DSA	I (%)	SM	DSA	I (%)	SM
IP	5.37	78.96	4.05	6.57	80.83	4.33
NIP	23.67	1.33	1.04	20.15	12.44	1.2
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

IP: inoculated plants ; NIP: non inoculated plants

• Comparison of nine cowpea plants

Significant differences were obtained following Kruskal-Wallis bilateral statistical test (Table 3). For all cultivars, symptoms developed earlier in 2015 (5-7 DSA) whereas in 2016 cultivars Tiligré and Yiis-yandé developed symptoms very late (15-16 DSA). Cultivars Yiis-yandé and Tiligré exhibited the lowest incidences, <7 % (Tiligré) and <28 % (Yiis-yandé) in both experiments. The other cultivars reached 100 % incidence except for Nafi, in the 2015 experiment with 64.68 %. Symptom severity within Tiligré and Yiis-yandé cultivars were low (SM<2) at the end of 28 days observation whereas disease severity was very high in cultivars Gorom local and Moussa local (5.96<SM<6) and fairly high (3.28<SM<5) for the others. Altogether, disease incidence and symptom severity were the most differential resistance traits (Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of the resistance of cowpea cultivars to CPMoV based on the day after inoculation at which symptoms appeared (DSA), disease incidences (I %) and symptom severities (SM). (Kruskal-Wallis bilateral statistical test).

Cultivars	Trial in 2015			Trial in 2016		
	DSA	I (%)	SM	DSA	I (%)	SM
Yiis-yandé	5 a	27,78 a	1,64 a	15 a	11,67 a	1,32 a
Tiligré	7 a	4,17 a	1,04 a	16 a	6,67 a	1,08 a
Nafi	6,33 a	64,68 b	3,28 b	5 b	100 b	5 b
Gourgou	5 a	96,67 c	4,73 c	5 b	96,67 b	4,87 b
Komcallé	5 a	100 c	4,24 c	5 b	100 b	5 b
Niizwé	5,66 a	100 c	4,37 c	5 b	100 b	5 b
Moussa local	5 a	100 c	6 d	5 b	100 b	5,96 c
Gorom local	5 a	100 c	6 d	5 b	100 b	6 c
Kvx61-1	5,67 a	100 c	5 c	5 b	100 b	5 b

When the p-value is less than 5 % there is a different letter and when it is over 5 % there the same letter.

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) distinguished three groups of cultivars according to their susceptibility/resistance against CPMoV (Figure 2). Group 1 comprised the cultivars Yiis-yandé and Tiligré that are considered to be resistant to CPMoV; Group 2 comprises the cultivars, Gorom local and Moussa local and group 3 comprise all the other cultivars considered to be fairly susceptible.

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Figure 2: Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering (AHC) highlighting three groups of cowpea cultivars resistance to cowpea mottle virus in Burkina Faso

Effect of cowpea mottle virus on pods and grains yields

Analyse of variance (ANOVA statistical test) indicated overall that non-inoculated (NIP) plants are significantly different from inoculated (IP) plants irrespective of the yield trait and the year of the experiment (Table 4). Numbers of pods and grain weight are the most contrasting traits (30.89 % and 31.26 % in yield losses respectively) whereas the number of grains per five pods was less contrasting trait (16.76 % in yield losses).

Table 4: Grains and pods yields losses due to the infection of CPMoV (ANOVA statistical test)

	2015			2016		
	Pods No.	Grain weight (g)/plant	Grain No./5 pods	Pods No.	Grain weight (g)/plant	Grain No./5 pods
NIP	19.35 a	21.44 a	38.85 a	20.46 a	25.16 a	44.5 a
IP	14.1 b	14.79 b	32.34 b	14.14 b	17.294 b	39.92 b
Yield loss (%)	27.13	31.02	16.76	30.89	31,26	10.29
P-value	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001

NIP: non inoculated plants; IP: inoculated plants; No: number

High significant decreases of pods number were recorded in 2015 and 2016 for several inoculated cultivars, including Gorom local, Moussa local and Niizwé cultivars that proved to be the most affected cultivars (Table 5). In contrast, no difference was detected with cultivars Tiligré, Yiis-yandé and Gourgou. Indeed, Pod numbers ranged from 10.1 to 24.6 on inoculated plants against 12-26.3 on non-inoculated plants in 2015. In 2016, it ranged from 4.8 to 21.6 on inoculated plants against 16.3 to 24.1 in 2016 on non-inoculated plants. These resulted in yield losses from 6.67 to 54.34 % in 2015 and 1.82 to 76.92 % in 2016.

High significant decreases of grains weight were observed for all cultivars except Tiligré and Yiis-yandé (Table 5). While in inoculated plots grains weight varied from 4.9 to 28.2, it was from 10.3 to 28.1 in non-inoculated plots during 2015. In the same order in 2016, grains' weight was from 4.7 to 29.2 against 19.9 to 33.9. Then, the grain yield loss ranged from 0.57

Table 5: Cowpea pod and grain yields losses due to *cowpea mottle virus*

Pod yield losses						
Cultivars	Pods No/plant (2015)			Pods No/plant (2016)		
	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)
Yiis-yandé	17.8 a	16.1 a	-10.48	14.3 a	16.3 a	12.4
Tiligré	24.6 a	26.3 a	6.67	21.6 a	22 a	1.82
Nafi	15.1 a	22.4 b	32.69	14.9 a	22.3 b	32.93
Gourgou	15.7 a	19.8 a	20.91	13.6 a	18.2 a	25.12
Komcallé	13 a	17.7 b	26.53	21.1 a	24.1 a	12.34
Niizwé	5.5 a	12 b	54.34	14.1 a	21.3 b	33.89
Moussa local	11.5 a	19.8 b	42.04	4.8 a	20.8 b	76.92
Gorom local	10.1 a	19.1 b	47.47	8.1 a	19.5 b	58.36
Kvx61-1	14.5 a	20 b	27.33	13.5 a	22.4 b	39.58
Grain weight yield losses						
Cultivars	Grain weight (g)/plant (2015)			Grain weight (g)/plant (2016)		
	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)
Yiis-yandé	22.9 a	19.4 a	-18.13	22.9 a	24 a	4.83
Tiligré	28.2 a	28.1 a	-0.57	29.2 a	27.5 a	-6.19
Nafi	19.9 a	28.1 b	29.16	18.8 a	30.9 b	39.04
Gourgou	14.7 a	24 b	38.74	14.9 a	24.7 b	39.67
Komcallé	14.1 a	22.4 b	36.77	25.1 a	33.9 b	26
Niizwé	4.9 a	10.3 b	52.66	13.4 a	19.9 b	32.78
Moussa local	10.6 a	20.1 b	47.31	4.7 a	23.2 b	79.67
Gorom local	7.5 a	20.4 b	63.14	9.5 a	21 b	54.68
Kvx61-1	12.8 a	22.2 b	42.46	10.8 a	22.5 b	51.98
Grain number yield losses						
Cultivars	Grain No/5 pods (2015)			Grain No/5 pods (2016)		
	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)	IP	NIP	Yield loss (%)
Yiis-yandé	34.7 a	37.9 a	8.49	40.9 a	45.4 a	9.87
Tiligré	38.1 a	39.5 a	3.5	42.5 a	39.9 a	-6.65
Nafi	34.9 a	40 a	12.72	43.9 a	48.7 a	9.9
Gourgou	27.7 a	35.3 b	21.61	37.7 a	43.2 b	12.67
Komcallé	32.8 a	36.7 a	10.54	45.7 a	47.5 a	3.88
Niizwé	29.7 a	39.6 b	25.21	37.4 a	39 a	4.07
Moussa local	30.3 a	38.7 b	21.86	27.7 a	50.2 b	44.8
Gorom local	24.9 a	38.4 b	35.12	33.2 a	42 b	20.88
Kvx61-1	36.6 a	44.2 b	17.38	35.5 a	44.8 b	20.77

Z bilateral statistical test was used to compare inoculated (IP) and non-inoculated plants (NIP). While a p-value <0.05 is depicted by two different letters, a p-value >0.05 is depicted by the same letter; V1 (Yiis-yandé); V2 (Tiligré); V3 (Nafi); V4 (Gourgou); V5 (Komcallé); V6 (Niizwé); V7 (Moussa local); V8 (Gorom local) and V9 (Kvx61-1).

to 63.14 % in 2015 and 4.83 to 79.67 % in 2016. Noteworthy, cultivars Gorom local, Moussa local, Niizwé and Kvx61-1 were the most affected by CPMoV infection.

Grains' number per pod was the less contrasting yield trait (Table 5). Indeed, it presents a weak level of yield loss when varied from 3.5 to 35.12 % in 2015 and 3.88 to 44.8 % in 2016. Nevertheless, Gorom local and Moussa local still the most affected cultivars by CPMoV infection. Thus, on inoculated plants, seed numbers per five pods ranged from 24.9 to 38.1 against 35.3 to 44.2 in 2015 and 27.7 to 45.7 against 39 to 50.2 in 2016, when comparing inoculated and non-inoculated plants.

Correlation analyses between disease incidence and severity, and pod and grain yields

All cultivars taken together, the Pearson statistical test determined a negative correlation between disease incidence and pod numbers (2015) or grain weights (2015 and 2016) and between severity and pod numbers (2015 and 2016) or grain weights (2015 and 2016) (Table 6). In contrast, except for disease severity (2015), no significant correlation was identified for grain numbers per pod. In addition, no correlation was observed with the days of symptoms appearance. Then, virus incidence and severity mean might be the main factors that decrease cowpea yield.

Table 6: Correlation between disease incidence and severity and pod and grain yields

	2015			2016		
	DSA	I %	SM	DSA	I %	SM
Pods No.	-0,030	-0,51**	-0,45*	-0,010	-0,340	-0,45*
Grain weight	0,010	-0,58**	-0,54**	0,140	-0,53**	-0,59**
Grain No./5pods	-0,070	-0,320	-0,4*	0,020	-0,220	-0,360

Pearson statistical test was applied. (**) when P-value is less than 1% and (*) when the p-value is less than 5 %. No, number

Seed transmission

Unexpectedly, none cowpea seed transmission was observed over the 818 germinated seedlings observed. Moreover when tested in back inoculation no positive detection was observed. Neither resistant nor susceptible cultivars successfully transmitted CPMoV by seeds.

DISCUSSION

This study reports for the first time the effect of CPMoV on several cowpea cultivars in Burkina Faso.

We showed that cultivars could be classified into three groups according to their susceptibility/resistance against CPMoV (Figure 2). Group 1 is composed of two cultivars (Yiis-yandé and Tiligré) that are considered to be resistant to CPMoV; Group 2 has two susceptible cultivars Gorom local and Moussa local and the group 3 constitute of fairly susceptible cultivars to which belong the other cultivars.

Overall, the negative effect of CPMoV on susceptible and fairly susceptible cultivars is correlated with substantial decreases in pods numbers and grain weight. Several studies led by (Taiwo and Akinjogunla, 2006), (Kareem and Taiwo, 2007) and (Nsa and Kareem, 2015) focusing on the effect of CPMoV and other cowpea-infecting viruses suggest that pods numbers and grain weight yield losses could probably be associated with decreased flowering rates due to high levels of flowers abortion (up to 100%) and weak filling and nutritive reserve accumulation in grains, respectively. Additionally, a recently study that was assessing the effect of the same isolate of CPMoV on Bambara groundnut in Burkina Faso (Zongo et al., 2018) revealed a high incidence of this virus, a high flowers number decreases and high grain losses (83.9 %). These susceptible and fairly susceptible cultivars might thus initiate an early epidemic hearth under field's conditions according to their very early symptom appearance (05 days).

Other parts, results confirmed the high susceptibility of local cultivars Gorom local and Moussa local to virus disease, as reported by Konate and Neya (1996); Neya et al. (2015) and Barro et al. (2016a).

In resistant cultivars Yiis-yande and Tiligre, the resistant gene mechanism might be to prevent the viral infection or to maintain the virus titer at a low level according to their low disease incidence (4.17-27.78 %) and severity less than 1.64. In the same way, Bashir et al. (2002b); Longue Sokpe et al. (2018) working on resistance to respectively Blackeye cowpea mosaic virus and Rice yellow mottle virus demonstrated that resistant accessions had a very low virus titer and severity compared to susceptible ones.

Our study does not confirm previous results of Allen et al. (1982) who found that cowpea mottle virus may be seed transmissible at a very low rate (0.4%) in susceptible cultivars. However, they got no seed transmission with resistant cultivars as we found in this study. Moreover, our results are in agreement with Thouvenel et al. (1990) who didn't find any seed transmission of cowpea mottle virus even if they tested

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only 100 seeds from infected plants. This may be supposed that cultivars tested in this study have a good genetic potential to stop cowpea mottle virus propagation through seed. As seed transmission is a critical feature to be considered in setting relevant management procedures of the disease, seed transmission tests will have to be repeated to clarify the inconsistency of the results.

Overall, our study reveals that the majority of cowpea cultivars currently grown in Burkina Faso are susceptible to CPMoV, which suggests that this virus might become a veritable constrain of cowpea production in the country. In addition, (Nsa and Kareem, 2015) have reported that the CPMoV effect can be even stronger in cases of co-infection with CABMV or Southern cowpea mosaic virus (SCPMV), two viruses that are occurring in Burkina Faso (Palanga et al. 2016). Nevertheless, the use of resistant cultivars, such as Tiligre and Yiis-yande by farmers and in the breeding program might contribute to improve cowpea infecting-virus control in Burkina Faso and prevent a CPMoV surge in this country.

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to improve cowpea virus control in Burkina Faso. Using mechanical inoculation and cowpea mottle virus isolate BE 273, resistant, fairly susceptible and susceptible cultivars were identified in the country. When resistant and fairly susceptible cultivars resulted from crossbreeding programs, susceptible cultivars still local. Although high yield loss was observed on susceptible cultivars, resistant genotype showed a good potential to control the cowpea mottle virus. This study must be extended to another local cultivar from Burkina Faso to identify a high source of resistance to the cowpea mottle virus.

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REFERENCES

- i. Aboki, E., Yuguda, R., 2013. *Determinant of Profitability in Cowpea Production in Takum Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. J Agri Sci* 4 (1), 33-37.
- ii. Adegbite, A.A., Amusa, N.A., 2008. *The major economic field diseases of cowpea in the humid agro-ecologies of South-western Nigeria. Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 7 (25) 4706-4712.
- iii. Agyeman, K., Berchie, J.N., Osei-Bonsu, I., E., T.N., Fordjour, J.K., 2014. *Growth and Yield Performance of Improved Cowpea (Vigna Unguiculata L.) Varieties in Ghana. Agricultural Science* 2, 44-52.
- iv. Aliyu, O.M., Lawal, O.O., Wahab, A.A., Ibrahim, U.Y., 2019. *Evaluation of Advanced Breeding Lines of Cowpea (Vigna unguiculata L. Walp) for High Seed Yield under Farmers' Field Conditions. Plant Breed. Biotech.* 7 (1), 12-23.
- v. Allen, D.J., Thottappilly, G., Rossel, H.W., 1982. *Cowpea mottle virus: field-resistance and seed transmission in virus-tolerant cowpea. Ann. Appl. Biol.* 100, 331-336.
- vi. Barro, A., Sawadogo, M., Kiebre, Z., Neya, B.J., 2016a. *Evaluation de la résistance de quelques lignées et écotypes de niébé (Vigna unguiculata (L.) WALP.) au Cowpea Aphid-Borne Mosaic Virus au Burkina Faso. International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies* 15 (2), 387-394.
- vii. Barro, A., Tignegre, J., Dieni, Z., Kiebre, Z., Poda, L., Sawadogo, M., 2016b. *Inheritance and the Allelic Relationship of Resistance to Cowpea Aphid Borne Mosaic Virus (CABMV) in Two Cowpea Genotypes, KVX640 and KVX396-4-5-2D, in Burkina Faso. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 5 (8), 285-292.
- viii. Bashir, M., Ahmad, Z., Ghafoor, A., 2002a. *Cowpea aphid-borne mosaic potyvirus: A review. Int. J. Pest Manage.* 48 (2), 155-168.
- ix. Bashir, M., Ahmad, Z., Ghafoor, A., 2002b. *Cowpea germplasm evaluation for virus resistance under greenhouse conditions. Asian Journal of Plant Sciences* 2 (1), 585-587.

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- x. Boukar, O., Fatokun, C.A., Huynh, B.-L., Roberts, P.A., Close, T.J., 2016. *Genomic Tools in Cowpea Breeding Programs: Status and Perspectives*. *Front. Plant Sci.* 7, 757.
- xi. Dzemo, W.D., Niba, A.S., Asiwe, J.A.N., 2010. *Effects of insecticide spray application on insect pest infestation and yield of cowpea [Vigna unguiculata (L.) Walp.] in the Transkei, South Africa*. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 9 (11), 1673-1679.
- xii. Faostat, 2016. *Crop production*. *Fao*, <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>.
- xiii. Gumedzoe, M.Y., Sunu, D.Y., Thottappilly, G., Asselin, A., 1990. *Importance of the cowpea mottle virus and cowpea yellow mosaic-virus in togo*. *Phytoprotection* 71, 85-91.
- xiv. Hall, A.E., Cisse, N., Thiaw, S., Elawad, H.O.A., Ehlers, J.D., Ismail, A., Fery, R., Roberts, P., Kitch, L.W., Murdock, L.L., Boukar, O., Phillips, R.D., McWatters, K.H., 2003. *Development of cowpea cultivars and germplasm by the Bean/Cowpea CRSP*. *Field Crops Res* 82, 103-134.
- xv. Hampton, R.O., Thottappilly, G., 2003. *Cowpea in: Loebenstein, G., Thottappilly, G. (Eds.), Virus and virus-like diseases of major crops in developing countries Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic, pp. 355-376*.
- xvi. Hema, M., Sreenivasulu, P., Patil, B.L., Kumar, P.L., Reddy, D.V.R., 2014. *Tropical Food Legumes: Virus Diseases of Economic Importance and Their Control*. *Advances in Virus Research* 90, 1-76.
- xvii. Kareem, K.T., Taiwo, M.A., 2007. *Interactions of viruses in cowpea: effects on growth and yield parameters*. *Virol. J.* 4, 7.
- xviii. Konate, G., Neya, B.J., 1996. *Rapid detection of cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus in cowpea seeds*. *Ann. Appl. Biol.* 129, 261-266.
- xix. Langyintuo, A.S., Lowenberg, D.J., 2006. *Potential regional trade implication of adopting Bt cowpea in West and Central Africa Back Issues Index* 9 (2), 38-42.
- xx. Longue Sokpe, R.D., Traore, V.S.E., Zinga, I., Asante, M.D., Bouda, Z., Neya, J.B., Barro, N., Traore, O., 2018. *Pathogenicity of rice yellow mottle virus and screening of rice accessions from the Central African Republic*. *Virol. J.* 15 (6) 1-9.
- xxi. Modu, Y., Putai, A.J., Petu-Ibikunle, A.M., 2010. *An economic analysis of cowpea production among women farmers in Askira/Uba local government area Borno State Nigeria*. *Afr. J. Gen. Agric.* 6, 7-17.
- xxii. Neya, B.J., Zida, P.E., Sereme, D., Lund, O.S., Traore, O., 2015. *Evaluation of Yield Losses Caused by Cowpea Aphid-borne mosaic virus (CABMV) in 21 Cowpea (Vigna unguiculata (L.) Walp.) Varieties in Burkina Faso*. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 18, 304-313.
- xxiii. Nielson, S.S., Brandt, W.E., Singh, B.B., 1993. *Genetic variability for nutritional composition and cooking time of improved cowpea lines*. *Crop Sci* 33, 469-472.
- xxiv. Nsa, I.Y., Kareem, K.T., 2015. *Additive interactions of unrelated viruses in mixed infections of cowpea (Vigna unguiculata L. Walp)*. *Front. Plant Sci.* 6, 812.
- xxv. Palanga, E., Filloux, D., Martin, D.P., Fernandez, E., Gargani, D., Ferdinand, R., Zabre, J., Bouda, Z., Neya, J.B., Sawadogo, M., Traore, O., Peterschmitt, M., Roumagnac, P., 2016. *Metagenomic-Based Screening and Molecular Characterization of Cowpea- Infecting Viruses in Burkina Faso*. *PLoS One* 11(10), e0165188.
- xxvi. Palanga, E., Martin, D.P., Galzi, S., Zabre, J., Bouda, Z., Neya, J.B., Sawadogo, M., Traore, O., Peterschmitt, M., Roumagnac, P., Filloux, D., 2017. *Complete genome sequences of cowpea polerovirus 1 and cowpea polerovirus 2 infecting cowpea plants in Burkina Faso*. *Arch Virol*, 1-4.
- xxvii. Shoyinka, S.A., Bozarth, R.F., Reese, J., Rossel, H.W., 1978. *Cowpea mottle virus: a seed-borne virus with distinctive properties infecting cowpea in Nigeria*. *Phytopathology* 68, 693-699.
- xxviii. Taiwo, M.A., Akinjogunla, O.J., 2006. *Cowpea viruses: Quantitative and qualitative effects of single and mixed viral infections*. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 5, 1749-1756.
- xxix. Taiwo, M.A., Kareem, K.T., Nsa, I.Y., Hughes, J.D., 2007. *Cowpea viruses: Effect of single and mixed infections on symptomatology and virus concentration*. *Virol. J.* 4, 1-5.
- xxx. Taiwo, M.A., Shoyinka, S.A., 1988. *Viruses infecting cowpeas in Africa with special emphasis on the potyviruses*, in: *Williams, A.O., Mbiele, A.L., Nkouka, N. (Eds.), Virus diseases of plants in Africa. OAU/STRC Scientific Publication, Lagos, Nigeria, pp. 93-115*

April 30, 2020

- xxxi. *Thouvenel, J.C., Tia, E., Fishpool, L.D.C., 1990. Characterization of cowpea mottle virus on cowpea (Vigna unguiculata) in the Ivory Coast and the identification of a new vector. Trop. Agric. 67 (3), 279-282.*
- xxxii. *Vaillancourt, R.E., Weeden, N.F., 1992. Chloroplast DNA Polymorphism Suggests Nigerian Center of Domestication for the Cowpea, Vigna unguiculata (Leguminosae). American Journal of Botany 79 (10), 1194-1199.*
- xxxiii. *Zongo, E., Néya, B.J., Traore, V.S.E., Palanga, E., Zabré, J., Barro, N., Traoré, O., 2018. Impact of Cowpea mottle virus on the Growth and Yield of Bambara Groundnut (Vigna subterranea (L.) Verdc.). American Journal of Plant Sciences 9, 2053-2062.*